

Switching off the label 'women in tech'

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The focus of the talk is on the ways in which women are discursively constructed in the context of professional spaces in tech clusters. This is to give time to consider how the label “women in tech” (WiT) is dominated by the masculine perspective of tech work and characterised by how individuals perform “identity work”. It has become apparent that the WiT label was already being used as shorthand for a problem very much with a name and her name is “woman”.

The casual use of the label is significant. While notable as a term in industry and policy, the visibility and dysfunction of the new problems at play through the WiT label are more complex, loaded and woven through the backbone of this talk.